

Histopathological Overview of Inflammatory Lesions of Gastrointestinal Tract at Tertiary Care Center of North Maharashtra**Deepak Shejwal¹, Bharat Borole², Kunal Deore³, Pooja Laxman Khandwe⁴, Shraddha Anil Paithankar⁵**¹Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Government Medical College Jalgaon, Maharashtra, India²Professor, Department of Pathology, Government Medical College Jalgaon, Maharashtra, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Government Medical College Jalgaon, Maharashtra, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Government Medical College Jalgaon, Maharashtra, India⁵Junior Resident, Department of Pathology, Government Medical College Jalgaon, Maharashtra, India

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Inflammatory lesions of gastrointestinal tract (GIT) are most common conditions with high degree of morbidity. The variety of GI lesions using endoscopic biopsies was divided as esophageal, gastric, duodenal, and colonic lesions. In present study, we aim to understand and analyze histopathological spectrum in inflammatory lesions of gastrointestinal tract in tertiary care center of north Maharashtra.**Materials and Methods:** This was a retrospective observational study including tissue samples of 244 cases, submitted for histopathological evaluation from June 2022 to June 2023. The various inflammatory conditions were analyzed with reference to age, gender, clinical findings, gross and histopathology. Also hematoxylin and eosin stained formalin fixed and paraffin embedded tissue were received to study the histopathological features, microscopically.**Observations and Results:** The present study included a total cases of 244 cases out of which there were 77 cases (31.55%) of upper GI tract biopsies and remaining 167 cases (68.45%) were of lower GI tract biopsies. 57.79% were males while 42.21% were females while peak incidence in 3rd and 4th decades. Among 77 (100%) cases of upper GI biopsies, chronic duodenitis (22.07%) was the most common in inflammatory lesions followed by chronic gastritis (18.19%). In lower GI tract biopsies, out of 167 (100%), Acute on chronic appendicitis (35.92%) was the most common.**Conclusion:** The present study provides a reasonable picture of the demographic features and clinicopathological manifestations of patients of tertiary care center in north Maharashtra for inflammatory lesions in GIT. Histopathological evaluation is a gold standard for early detection of GI lesions enlightens on early diagnosis by histopathology beneficial for the patients in north Maharashtra.**Keywords:** Histopathology, Inflammatory Lesions, Gastrointestinal Tract, North Maharashtra.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Gastrointestinal tract (GIT) are one of the most common pathologic entities we came across in our day to day practice with high degree of morbidity, including both benign as well as malignant lesions, the spectrum of disease can involve individual or combination of GIT segments.

GIT is a hollow tube extending from the oral cavity to the anus that consists of anatomically distinct segments including the esophagus, stomach, small intestine, colon, rectum, and anus [1].

Mostly, cases received for evaluation are mainly endoscopic biopsies which have the advantage of being used as both diagnostically and therapeutically. [2] Majority received endoscopic biopsies, where inflammatory lesions are found out to be more common. The primary aim of GI pathology is to provide essential diagnostic and prognostic information allowing physicians and surgeons the best clinical management of the individual patient. [3] We have attempted to analyse the various inflammatory lesions in our study under clinicoradiological guidance with the

final diagnosis interpreted on histopathological examination.

In present study, we aim to understand and analyse histopathological spectrum in inflammatory lesions of gastrointestinal tract, in tertiary care centre of North Maharashtra. To correlate GIT spectrum with age, sex and site of lesions in tertiary care center of North Maharashtra.

Material & Methods

This was a retrospective observational study including tissue samples of 244 cases submitted for histopathological evaluation. The study period of one year from June 2022 To June 2023 in department of pathology, government medical college, Jalgaon, Maharashtra.

All the presenting upper and lower GIT endoscopic biopsy specimens received during the period were included in this study.

The specimen were processed for microscopic examinations after grossing, proper sectioning, fixation, paraffin blocking, microtome cutting and hematoxyline and eosin (H & E) staining. The various inflammatory conditions were analysed with using variables as age, gender, clinical findings, gross and histopathology.

Original images of the microscopic presentation of various lesions were captured.

Results

The study was conducted in Department of Pathology in government Medical College, Jalgaon on total of 244 cases of GIT endoscopic biopsies during period one year as follows:

Figure 1: Distribution of Inflammatory GI lesions as per Site

The study included 77 [31.55%] biopsies of upper GI tract out of which most common site is duodenum with 61%, 26% of stomach and 13% of oesophagus. Lower GI tract with maximum 167 [68.45%] cases out of which most common site is

appendix [66.46%], followed by small intestine, caecum, colon, rectum and anal canal, as shown in figure no.1. When segregated, we came across many nonspecific inflammatory lesions in which particular diagnosis could not be made.

Figure 2: Distribution of Inflammatory GI lesions as per age

As shown in figure no.2, Among 244 cases analysed, 21 -40 years of age group was the most commonly affected with 75 cases [30.73%].The youngest patient was 2 day old with chronic nonspecific inflammation of jejunum and oldest one of age 85 years is with Ulcerative colitis.

Figure 3: Distribution of Inflammatory GI lesions as per Sex

There was male preponderance noted in our study with 141 [57.79%] cases. 103 [42.21%] were seen in females. Male to female ratio of 1.37: 1 was noted as shown in figure no. 3.

The table no. 1 shows that among the 77 (100 %) cases of upper GI biopsies, chronic duodenitis with 17cases (22.07%) was the most common in

inflammatory lesions followed by chronic gastritis with 14 cases (18.19%).

Four cases showing dysplastic changes as oesophagitis with squamous dysplasia, Acute on chronic ulcerative oesophagitis with moderate dysplasia, Hypertrophic gastritis with mild dysplasia, Barrett oesophagus with mild dysplasia.

Table 1: Distribution of Inflammatory GI lesions as per Histo-Pathological diagnosis:

Diagnosis	UGIT = 77			LGIT = 167					Total
	Oeso phagus	Sto mach	Duodenum	Small Intestine & Caecum	Colon	Rectum	Anal Canal	Appen dix	
Acute Inflammation	6	1	-	1	-	-	-	18	26
Chronic Inflammation	-	4	7	1	-	1	4	60	77

Acute on chronic Inflammation	2	14	17	12	7	-	-	30	82
Eosinophilic Inflammation	-	-	11	1	-	-	-	-	12
Tuberculosis	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1
Inflammatory Bowel Disease	-	-	-	5	3	1	-	-	9
Ulcerative Lesion	-	-	11	2	-	6	-	-	19
Necrotic/Gangrene	-	-	-	6	-	-	-	1	7
Inflammation with Dysplasia	2	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	4
Perforation	-	-	-	2	1	-	-	2	5
Obstruction	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	2
Total	10	20	47	32	12	8	4	111	244

In lower GI tract biopsies, out of 167 (100%) cases, Acute on chronic appendicitis (35.92%) was the most commonly observed followed by chronic appendicitis.

Lowest affecting age is a three month female child diagnosed as Meckel’s diverticulitis with ileoileal intussusception. Eosinophilic duodenitis occurred in 11 cases. Inflammatory bowel disease [IBD] observed in 9 cases. Out of cases 9 cases of IBD, Ulcerative colitis with 7 cases more commonly seen than Crohn’s disease with 2 cases. One case with Tuberculosis in 80-year-old female at ileocaecal junction.

Discussion

The study was conducted between June 2022 to June 2023 dealing with 244 cases of gastrointestinal endoscopic biopsies, considering the factors such as age, sex and site of the patients.

Of these case reports considered, there were 10 cases of oesophagus biopsies, 20 cases of stomach and 47 cases were of duodenum. In inflammatory lesions of lower GIT, 32 cases of small intestine and caecal region, 12 cases of colon, 8 cases of rectum, 4 cases of anal canal and 111 cases of appendix.

Figure 4: Koilocytic oesophagitis with mild dysplasia

Figure 5: Herpes esophagitis

Figure 6: Eosinophilic esophagitis

Figure 7: Barrett's Esophagus

Figure 8: Crohn's disease

Figure 9: Ulcerative colitis

Figure 10: TB intestine

Figure 11: Amoebic colitis

In the present study, high incidence was observed between age group of third- and fourth-decade accounting for 30.73% overall case distribution. The age-related difference could be due to varied exposure to the risk factors among the different age groups especially in the relation to the dietary habits of both qualitative and quantitative. The lesion

of GIT develops with a sequence of metaplasia which can sometimes lead to carcinoma. [4]

In aspect of sex distribution, male preponderance was noted when compared to female patient with a ratio of 1.37: 1. The gender ratio favoring male could be reflective of the fact that males are exposed to more risk than female in north Maharashtra.

Koilocytic oesophagitis with mild dysplasia is seen in 48-year-old female clinically diagnosed as esophageal stricture. On microscopy, stratified squamous epithelium shows hyperplasia with mild dysplasia and koilocytic changes in epithelium with eccentric hyperchromatic nuclei & perinuclear vacuoles is seen.[Fig.4] Also Herpes esophagitis seen in 42 year old male with dysphagia. On microscopy, multinucleated squamous giant cells with nuclear moulding and margination of the chromatin are seen. Large, eosinophilic ground glass intranuclear viral inclusions with a surrounding halo [Cowdry A bodies] present at the margins of the ulcer [Fig 5]. Eosinophilic esophagitis seen in 32-year-old male with ≥ 15 eosinophils per high power field present in the squamous mucosa [Fig 6]. Barrett's Esophagus 35 year old showed esophageal squamous epithelium replaced by columnar epithelium of intestinal type with goblet cells, on microscopy. [Fig 7]

Crohn's disease [Fig 8] histopathological examination shows Colonic mucosa with crypt distortion, inflammatory expansion of lamina propria with lympho-plasmacytosis. Cryptitis and crypt abscess with evident patchy mucosal ulceration. Neutrophils infiltration in peri-cryptal areas. Two areas show ill formed epithelioid granulomas. Ulcerative colitis shows extensive superficial ulcerated mucosa. Irregular gland lumina with glandular distortion evident. Crypt abscess shows PMN's and plasma cells and cryptitis seen. [Fig 9]

TB intestine [Fig 10] diagnosed in 80-Year-old female with weight loss, fever, abdominal pain. On gross, multiple superficial ulcers perpendicular to long axis of bowel seen. Microscopy shows necrotizing granulomatous inflammation, composed of central necrotic zone surrounded by epithelioid cells with multinucleated giant cells [Langhans's] and lymphocytes. Amoebic colitis is seen in 35-year-old female with worsening diarrhea and ab-

dominal pain. On gross, ulcers with yellowish and reddish exudates seen. HPE shows cryptitis with PMN's, lymphocytes. Trophozoites of *Entamoeba histolytica* which are round nucleus with peripherally condensed ring of chromatin and central dot-like karyosome. [Fig 11]

Conclusion

- The present study provides a reasonable picture of the demographic features and clinicopathological manifestations of patients of tertiary care centre in north Maharashtra for inflammatory lesions in gastrointestinal tract.
- Histopathological evaluation is the gold standard for the early detection of GI tract lesions as it helps in their early management.
- Our study of gastrointestinal tract lesions enlightens on early diagnosis by histopathology beneficial for the patients in north Maharashtra.

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